

The London Missionary Society in British Guiana, 1800-1824

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The London Missionary Society (LMS) was a group of evangelical Christians based in England. Formed in the late 18th century, their representatives were drawn from several Protestant denominations and tended to be working class people who were educated by the LMS for their profession as missionaries. In 1807 a Demerara (British Guiana, now Guyana) planter wrote to the LMS requesting a missionary specifically to minister to the enslaved on his plantation and those nearby. As with previous attempts by Christian missionaries in the area, this was seen by other slaveholders to be a danger to their authority and likely to lead to rebellion among the enslaved. The first LMS missionary to arrive was John Wray, who preached and taught in Demerara and neighbouring Berbice from 1808 until his death in 1837. The second LMS missionary to arrive was John Smith in 1817, who replaced John Wray when he left his post at plantation Le Resouviner. Known as the "Demerara Martyr", Smith was imprisoned in 1823 on suspicion of instigating one of the three major rebellions of enslaved people in the British Caribbean during the "Age of Abolition." Tried by court martial, Smith was found guilty and sentenced to death by hanging. He died in prison of tuberculosis before a stay of execution arrived from England. The death toll among the enslaved numbered in the hundreds and included Smith's head deacon, the enslaved man Quamina, while only two white people were killed. When news of the events arrived in England, protests over slavery and the treatment of the missionary were widespread. The governor of Demerara, John Murray, was recalled to England, and the following year, heated debates in British Parliament about the matter had important ramifications toward the abolition of slavery in the British colonies. Although the time period covered here is a short one, the impact on the colony and upon slavery in the British Caribbean was enormous. In the wake of the 1823 rebellion, missionaries affiliated with the LMS faced harrassment and slander, and the chapel in Demerara was burned. Popular and political pressure from England eventually prevailed and the actions of the enslaved rebels are credited toward eventual emancipation in the British Caribbean.

Date Range: 1800 CE - 1824 CE

Region: British Guiana

Region tags: Guyana, British Guiana

British Guiana circa 1800-1824, present day Guyana

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: da Costa, Emilia Viotti. "Crowns of Glory, Tears of Blood: The Demerara Slave Rebellion of 1823." Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1994.

- Source 2: Matthews, Gelien. "Caribbean Slave Revolts and the British Abolitionist Movement." Baton Rouge: Louisiana University Press, 2006.
- Source 3: Craton, Michael, "Testing the Chains: Resistance to Slavery in the British West Indies." Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 1982: 267-290.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://web-p-ebSCOhost-com.proxy.hil.unb.ca/ehost/detail/detail?vid=0&sid=ce6e6303-1809-49af-a389-fef32f2fde93%40redis&bdata=JnNpdGU9ZWhvc3QtbGl2ZSdzY29wZTlzaXRI#AN=11068255&db=aph>
- Source 1 Description: Smith, Clair. "Education as an Integral Part of Mission in a Slave-Led Congregation: A Case Study of the Guyana Congregational Union 1808-1848"
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/146646506006>
- Source 2 Description: Dierksheide, Christa. 'Missionaries, Evangelical Identity, and the Religious Ecology of the Early the British Caribbean,' "American Nineteenth Century History," Vol. 7, No. 1: 63-88.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/0030923780180207>
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Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/historyoflondonm02love/page/318/mode/2up>
- Source 1 Description: Lovett, Richard. "The History of the London Missionary Society, 1795-1895." London: Henry Frowde, 1899.
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/lifelaboursofjoh00rain/page/n5/mode/2up>
- Source 2 Description: Wray, John and Rain, Thomas. "The Life and Labors of John Wray, Pioneer Missionary in British Guiana." London: John Snow & Co., 1892
- Source 3 URL: <https://digital.soas.ac.uk/CW00000086/00001/5x?search=john+%3dsmith+%3djournal>
- Source 3 Description: Journal of John Smith, Le Resouvenir, Demerara, 6 March, 1817 - 18 August, 1823

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Many who attended the LMS chapel were of African origins and in some cases still practised certain spiritual/healing arts. The elite members of the region tended to be nominally members of the Church of England or Dutch Reformed.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: While all were welcome to attend LMS meetings and services, they were primarily geared toward the enslaved. An important reason for keeping meetings open was to reassure slaveholders that rebellion was not being encouraged. See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith cited in Sources.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Those who followed African beliefs often converted or attended at the LMS chapel out of curiosity or for socializing. Members of the Church of England were opposed to the LMS on the basis of their status of bondspeople rather than over religion. See below.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Violent conflict occurred between elite members of the colony and members of the LMS church who tended to be primarily enslaved persons. The elite element perceived the evangelical church as promoting rebellion among bondspeople by teaching that they were equal under God. See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith, cited in Sources.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Based on specific ritual; however, all were invited to attend. See below re required rituals.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: There were no class prerequisites, but the LMS chapel was predominately attended by enslaved persons with a few free people.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: Young children were taught by the missionaries and assistants, but to be a baptised member had to be approved and therefore tended to be adults.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual of baptism signified the willingness of the supplicant to join and the willingness of the group to accept them, and supplicants were required to learn the catechism before being baptised. However, complete knowledge of the catechism and baptism was not required for attendance. See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith cited above.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Attendance at services and adherence to the general rules of the group

Notes: Although this did not make a person a baptized member of the group, they were welcome to attend.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Newcomers were invited to attend by members, and missionaries would often ask people why they did not come to church. See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith cited above. The usual answer for not attending was their master had prohibited it.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– I don't know

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The home government in Britain supported the LMS and their missions in the Caribbean, by decree when deemed necessary. Local government, however, could be vehemently opposed depending on the inclination of the governor at the time. This issue was instrumental in sparking the 1823 uprising of enslaved persons in Demerara. See da Costa, *Crowns of Glory*: 3-38, cited in Sources.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There were several incidents of participants being denied baptism or being turned away from the church unless and until they renounced and changed the behaviour at issue. See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith cited in Sources.

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: Apostates were not physically prosecuted or punished, but being turned away from worship and meetings could be considered punishment.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because the members of the group were enslaved persons who were confined to specific plantations and subject to whether managers and overseers would allow attendance at any given time, it is almost impossible to give precise numbers. The group was also subject to how mobile they were, whether they were capable of sometimes walking long distances to attend. The journal of the missionary between 1817 and 1823 records wide variance in numbers in attendance, from as low as 25 to as high as 600.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See above answer re number of adherents. While there are some records indicating the number of enslaved persons on each plantation, this would give no indication as to whether they attended the LMS chapel or not.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: The group were Christians, but specifically adherents to the LMS chapel whose missionary was a member of the London Missionary Society in England.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The missionary, his wife and several deacons. Some others assisted in teaching on an ad hoc basis. See the Journal of John Smith; and Life and Labors of John Wray cited in Sources.

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The deacons and additional teachers were answerable to the missionary.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: The missionary was chosen by the directors of the LMS in England. The deacons and teachers were chosen by the missionary.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In particular circumstances other missionaries in the colony could write to the directors of the LMS in England. Directors could admonish or recall missionaries.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Notes: The governor of the colony could, and did, prohibit missionaries from certain actions. In the case of John Smith, he was charged with encouraging insurrection and was sentenced to death by hanging.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: In some matters the leader might admonish the follower for "un-Christian" behaviour. If the infraction was serious enough, there could be a vote among members as to whether the follower should be turned out of the group. However, followers often asked advice of the leader and engaged in debate. See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith, cited in Sources

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Bible

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Members were expected to learn the catechism via question and answer.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: Dependent on interpretation of the word of Christian god.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Dependent on interpretation of Christian scripture.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: New Testament - teachings of Jesus Christ as son of God to disciples.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: New Testament books of various disciples.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Not alterable, but interpreted into more modern language.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of the LMS, Protestant ministers.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders of other Protestant denominations would interpret the same scriptures, but were unlikely to have affected the members of this community.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: While missionaries were the official interpreters, members were free to discuss.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of the LMS missionaries in British Guiana during the time period in question, the missionaries, deacons, and other literate members would transmit the scriptures to the largely illiterate members.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The books of the Bible.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: During the period in question the places of worship were make-shift structures, or purpose-built but not monumental. See various entries in the Journal of John Smith and the Life and Labors of John Wray, cited in Sources.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: During the period in question, there were no structures of this type present that specifically

belonged to the LMS. Most places of worship at the time in the colony were make-shift or dual-purposed structures.

Is iconography present:

– I don't know

Notes: It is unlikely that iconography was present. This was an extremely poor, enslaved group of parishioners and the LMS was not a wealthy group. There may have been print pictures included in some books present, but there is no mention of them.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as a particular site would be considered sacred, they were buildings dedicated as chapels. These varied from a building contributed for the purpose on a plantation to an area within the town garrison used for worship. None of the sites used for worship by the LMS in British Guiana had a historically sacred reputation.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The Christian doctrine of life after death was particularly noted to impress upon enslaved adherents that they would be free of their physical suffering in the afterlife.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: See above answer.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The concept of bondspeople's bodies being owned by another was a difficult one for LMS missionaries to articulate their parishioners. Slaveholders were generally strongly opposed to Christian teachings for bondspeople, fearing rebellion. To avoid being denied access to teaching among the enslaved, LMS missionaries therefore attempted to stress that while their bodies were owned by another, their spirit was God's.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Followed basic Christian tenets.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Although "heaven" and "hell" were not specifically described in terms of location, they were generally thought of as "above" and "below."

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven for the good; hell for the bad.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven, where God dwelt, was vaguely "above" for those who lived good lives .

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: Hell was vaguely defined as "below" where those who did not live good lives were tormented for eternity.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: See above in terms of "above" and "below."

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: Not for that Christian group at that time.

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Usual in Christian burial at that time.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Assumed laid on back, legs and body extended, but this might not have been followed for all enslaved, particularly at times of a large number of corpses, for example, following rebellion.

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: See above answer regarding flexed corpses.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: As most enslaved adherents would have little or no personal possessions, it is unlikely that grave goods were present. Were simple Christian burials.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– I don't know

Notes: As of 1818, there was at least one public cemetery in British Guiana which had space for enslaved persons. It is unclear whether any of the LMS parishioners were buried there. Otherwise, most would have been buried on the plantation to which they belonged.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While it is not possible to know the location of all members' burial sites, it is likely some were not buried in a formal cemetery. In the case of executed members, of which there were a number, the location of their remains is generally unknown.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Some characteristics. Humans seen as being made in the Christian god's image.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The idea of the Christian god being "above" can be understood in the context of a sky deity.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: omnipotence and omnipresence

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: All-knowing

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Can cause anything to occur.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Events can be seen as a result of god's pleasure.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Events can be seen as the result of god's displeasure.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
 - Notes: God not seen as requiring food or drink.
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
 - Notes: This answer should be qualified, as scripture says that no other gods should come before God. However, God's son, Jesus Christ, was also worshipped.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: omnipresence
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Notes: Generally, no, although the scriptures describe communication with specific individuals, and some missionaries would describe their vocation as a "calling" from God.

↳ In dreams:

– No

Notes: There may have been some adherents who believed that they received communications in dreams, but generally, no.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The approved way to understand god was through the instruction of the missionary.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

Notes: See notes under Communication With the Living. The scriptures describe various types.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As authentic statements made by the enslaved adherents on this matter are non-existent, it is not known.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– I don't know

Notes: If the common Christian belief in angels was present, in all likelihood there was a belief that non-human supernatural beings were present. However, no specific mention of such an entity seems to have been made in documentation.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Generally thought of as angels. Some may have considered Jesus Christ as a supernatural being.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Within designated worship space.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: If including Christian symbology such as the cross as a sacred object.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Following Christian tenets such loving one's neighbour, Christ's love for humanity, Ten Commandments and other scripture.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Not killing another is one of the Christian Ten Commandments.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Killing another prohibited under the Christian Ten Commandments.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Not killing another is one of the Christian Ten Commandments.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Considered wrong to engage in sexual relations outside of marriage. In reality, the practice was common among the enslaved for a number of reasons, such as forceable separation from spouse, marriage not recognized by slaveholders, having multiple partners accepted in African religions, and the very common practice of enforced sex by owners on their bondspople.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Not approved of in Christianity or culturally.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– I don't know

Notes: Not documented, but assume common Christian and cultural aversion.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Lying against one of Christian Ten Commandments.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Particularly in reference to upholding Christian doctrine such as the Ten Commandments.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– I don't know

Notes: Assuming that supernatural beings such as angels care about missionaries' admonitions for enslaved adherents to obey their masters, laziness would be a concern. However, nothing documented seems to directly address the aspect of supernatural beings in this matter.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: The blanket term for African-based healing rituals was "obeah" which was commonly seen as sorcery among Christians. One particular LMS missionary, John Wray, counselled parishioners and those who were accused of being obeah practitioners on this being against Christian practices. See *Life and Labors of John Wray*, cited in Sources.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: If it is assumed that supernatural beings such as angels watched over adherents, one of the Christian Ten Commandments is to love one's neighbour, as well as missionaries promoting harmony between spouses. LMS missionaries counselled adherents on these topics.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

Notes: If "shirking risk" was to be interpreted as an enslaved member disobeying their master or otherwise rebelling, missionaries counselled against indulging in this behaviour. A missionary specifically implored one of his deacons not to take part in an intended uprising. This advice is, of course, not directly related to specific considerations of supernatural beings. See various incidents in the *Journal of John Smited*, cited in Sources.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: This topic has not appeared in known documentation. It might be assumed that culturally, Christians are expected to respect elders.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: This could be seen as going against the Christian commandment not to "bear false witness" against another. However, within slave studies, "gossip" is often used as simply a way to transfer news and information among a predominantly illiterate population.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: One of the Christian Ten Commandments is not to steal.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: A major area of contention in British Guiana during this time period was the argument over slaveowners forcing bondspeople to work on Sundays, leaving no time for worship on the designated Christian holy day. The issue was addressed by the home government in England, but slaveholders vehemently argued against allowing the time, and in some instances, did not allow bondspeople to leave their plantation to attend at the chapel. For further information on this topic, see Craton, Michael, "Empire, Enslavement and Freedom in the Caribbean" (Kingston, Jamaica: Ian Randle, 1997)

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Regular Sunday worship, sacraments of marriage, baptism, funerals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Missionaries encouraged as many people to attend worship as they could and argued with slaveowners who denied access to their bondspeople. If it is assumed that missionaries were doing the work commanded by God and were watched over, then it can be said that supernatural beings were concerned with this.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

Notes: Nothing in the known documentation seems to address this directly, but as missionaries stressed that bondspeople not fight against their masters, it could be inferred that economic concern was not a concern of supernatural beings. However, bondspeople did eventually rebel against slaveholders not giving them that which they felt they were entitled to, such as two free days a week in which to take care of their own concerns, which included economic. A missionary was held responsible for instigating the insurrection.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This would be open to interpretation. There is nothing which directly addresses hygiene in the documentation, but missionaries did not like the state of near-nakedness of some enslaved people. However, as the members were predominantly extremely impoverished bondspeople, it was understood that personal hygiene and/or dress was not a priority.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Christian God expected to allow spirit to enter heaven or send to hell, in which case Satan meted out punishment.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: Although god decrees who goes to heaven or hell in the afterlife, Satan metes out punishment. In some Protestant interpretations, Satan had minions in hell, but unknown what this group in particular believed.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Considering that God believed to be all-powerful and can cause events to occur.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Expected to live by Christian tenets and attend worship, if possible.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Following Christian tenets inhibits selfishness, particularly following Christ's example.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: The emphasis tended toward extreme punishment.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The idea of not being with God in heaven in the afterlife and being consigned to Hell to suffer punishment was fairly uniform in Protestant Christianity at this time.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is not a belief within Christianity.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is not a belief within Christianity.

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While such punishments are sometimes a belief in Protest Christianity, it does not appear to be raised among LMS missionaries in this particular place and time. Considering that most of the parishioners were enslaved, they were already suffering greatly. There was no indication that their oppressed state was a punishment for anything.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: The only way to get to heaven in the afterlife is through following Christian tenets.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Strong sense of community among the adherents. The group was expected to support one another.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Part of Christian belief to treat others as you would wish to be treated and to follow Christ's example.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The core belief was that the only way to reach heaven and be with God was to follow the Ten Commandments and Christ's teachings.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: The quantity of sensory pleasure is not specifically discussed. More important is the spiritual joy and absence of pain. However, if spiritual joy was seen as sensory pleasure, it would be considered much greater.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Although sensory pleasure is not specifically addressed in the afterlife, great spiritual joy and a complete absence of pain is. For enslaved people whose bodies had been tortured this might be considered an extreme sensory pleasure.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: Christianity does not consider reincarnation.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: Christianity does not consider reincarnation.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Being with God in the afterlife was considered the ultimate reward.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: This was not discussed among these missionaries, particularly as most adherents were enslaved people.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Refers to Jesus Christ in Jerusalem. Died, and arose from death.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The second coming of Christ the messiah is a question which remains unanswered today in Christianity. There is no documentation which specifies a date among the LMS documents.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Notes: See above answer regarding second coming in this lifetime.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: The idea of a second coming of Christ the messiah is prevalent in Christianity, although nothing specific is documented by the LMS in British Guiana.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of the second coming of Christ the messiah is prevalent in Christianity. It is not documented in scripture whether it would be in the near or distant future. Nothing documented specifically by LMS in British Guiana.

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: Part of Christian belief. Generally, the second coming would signify the end of the world as known when all good Christians would be gathered to god.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: Although Christ's primary importance was not seen as a political figure, he became one through his actions offending Roman rulers.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

Notes: Christ the messiah added to Jewish traditions to form the basis of Christianity, although Judaism remained.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Christ the messiah was seen as the son of God who was born in human form. He was to act as a teacher of God's will.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unknown time in Christian theology.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: Unknown time in future according to Christian theology.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unknown in Christianity whether in near or distant future.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unknown in Christian theology whether in near or distant future.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Only known to be at some future time.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: Follow Christian doctrine as given in the Bible.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: Christian concepts vary somewhat in interpretation. Unknown specifically what LMS missionaries described, other than that the good would be rewarded.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Varies according to interpretation in Christian beliefs. Unknown if LMS specifically described this event.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Interpretations vary according to Christian beliefs. Unknown if LMS missionaries specifically addressed this.

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No documentation from LMS in British Guiana.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Interpretations vary within Christianity. No documentation from LMS in British Guiana other than that the good would be with god.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Following the Ten Commandments and advice of scriptures were social norms in that formed a basis of how to live and treat others.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: This question is difficult to give a definitive answer because of the status of most of the

adherents to the group. Because they were primarily enslaved people, they were generally unable to have autonomy to follow convention or not. The emphasis would be more based on moral distinctions if they were able to follow Christian precepts. For example, an enslaved woman would often not want to commit adultery with a white man, but the convention in that place and time was that Black enslaved women were to be taken at a master's will.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Part of Christian Ten Commandments.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

Notes: Not emphasized in Christian doctrine, and as most adherents were enslaved, they were not expected to engage in battle, unless it was at the command of their master.

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: Christians in general were expected to show courage in holding fast to their beliefs, although being enslaved, many of the adherents of this group could not act against their master's wishes.

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: A basic Christian tenet.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: A basic Christian tenet.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: A basic Christian tenet.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: A basic Christian tenet.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Notes: A basic Christian tenet.

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Although this is a part of Christianity, as most of the adherents of this group were enslaved they did not have control over many aspects of their lives.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: This was emphasized by the LMS missionaries, primarily to avoid giving slaveholders anything to hold against the Christian teaching of bondspeople.

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: As part of basic Christian doctrine to honour one's parents, this was an important virtue. However, because most of the adherents were enslaved, they were not always able to follow this precept if it would run contrary to a master's commands.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Part of Christian doctrine. As well, LMS missionaries cautioned enslaved parishioners to show loyalty toward slaveowners to avoid being denied access to worship.

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: Being a part of the community was important to further the advancement of the missionaries' endeavours in the colony.

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

Notes: While not an important aspect of Christianity in general, this was particularly so in a group where most of the adherents were enslaved.

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: Although it was difficult for the primarily enslaved adherents to display anything other than frugality and moderation, there were instances where a great deal of alcohol could be consumed which was often accompanied by fighting and what was interpreted as lewd

dancing. Such behaviour was strongly opposed to by LMS missionaries. See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith, and the Life and Labors of John Wray, cited in Sources.

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: A tendency in most Christian doctrine, this was particularly important among the primarily enslaved adherents. Missionaries cautioned bondpeople against upsetting the status quo, which would result in curtailment in permission to worship.

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Notes: This was emphasized among the enslaved adherents and the missionaries who had a very difficult life in British Guiana.

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

Notes: Because of the enslaved status of most adherents and the difficulties faced by missionaries from slaveholders, such virtues were neither wise nor safe at that place and time.

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

Notes: Spiritual strength was emphasized rather than physical.

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: This is not part of basic Protestant Christian tenets, particularly among groups such as the LMS. Most adherents were enslaved, therefore they possessed none of these.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: Among the basic Protestant Christian tenets, particularly in this instance where most adherents were enslaved and missionaries generally were lower or middle class people.

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: While such virtues were generally encouraged by Christian missionaries in any case, since most of the adherents at this place and time were enslaved it was particularly important so as to avoid punishment and/or being denied access to worship.

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

Notes: While journals and letters from LMS missionaries in British Guiana profess joy in bringing the gospel to the enslaved, and in positive aspects of their lives, there was little emphasis placed on these traits as virtues. Most of the adherents were extremely oppressed as enslaved people and had very little joy in their physical lives.

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: Optimism and hope in obtaining reward in the afterlife was an important part of the LMS missionaries' message to their mostly enslaved parishioners. Otherwise, enslaved people had very little reason for either.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Generally a part of Christianity. While the enslaved adherents had very little to be thankful for, they were encouraged to be thankful for finding God, and for what little they had.

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: Reverence or awe toward God is a basic Christian precept.

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Most of Christian doctrine is based on faith. For the mostly enslaved adherents of the LMS missions in British Guiana, they had little else but faith and belief in reward in the afterlife.

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: Important for the missionaries to guide their parishioners. The missionaries, in turn, encouraged parishioners to make wise decisions when they had a choice, particularly when it came to religion.

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: Deacons of the church were chosen from among the (male) parishioners who showed the greatest understanding of scripture and were known for their sobriety and good judgment. Parishioners could be turned out of the church for repeatedly acting against Christian teachings and/or causing trouble. See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith, cited in Sources.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: Not important in Christianity.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

Notes: While culturally, most Christian groups value cleanliness, this was not something that could be much controlled among the mostly enslaved adherents who lived in extreme poverty and who were forced to work most of their waking hours.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The basic important virtues have been covered here.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Neither missionaries or parishioners are required to be celibate.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Some members had more than one wife as allowed in certain African religions (including Islam), and this seemed to be accepted to some degree if they had been together before converting to Christianity, particularly in respect to caring for their welfare. However, limiting themselves to one as a sexual partner was expected. Occasional references throughout the Journal of John Smith, cited in Sources.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: In the case of enslaved members, this restriction could be problematic. A woman might be committed to one partner, but enforced sex by slaveowners was common, in which case the woman was not held at fault if it was not her choice.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: As with most Christian groups, sex outside of marriage was frowned upon.

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: As with most Christian groups, sex outside of marriage was frowned upon. Missionaries recognized that females were always at risk of enforced sex by slaveowners.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: This would be considered murder and against Christian law.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: This would be considered murder and therefore against Christian law.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: This is against Christian law.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Although contributions toward books, chapel building, and donations to the missionary society were welcomed, parishioners were not required to give anything, particularly since they lived in extreme poverty and as enslaved persons had little or no personal property.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Regular attendance at meetings and worship was required, except if kept away by slaveowners or managers, or because of illness.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Physical risk taking was in no way required; however, some enslaved parishioners risked a beating from managers if they attended meetings after being denied access by the manager.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Members discovered engaging in perceived ethical misbehaviour could be turned away from participating, usually after the missionary would ask the group to weigh in on the issue.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Although private prayer was encouraged, enslaved members were usually working most of their waking hours and would have no time for formal prayer or worship.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Required if not prohibited by managers and overseers.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Highly variable. At certain crop seasons, during outbreaks of illness, or under official orders not to gather, there could be very few, while at other times large crowds would be present. (One missionary's journal recorded numbers as low as 25 and as high as 600+) See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith, and the Life and Labors of John Wray, cited in Sources. S

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 36

Notes: Number is based on worship occurring on Sundays and Wednesdays. There were often more services, depending on circumstances.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: From time to time, visiting missionaries would observe or take part in services. These were usually meant socially or as assistance, but occasionally letters would be sent to the directors of the LMS in England noting any concerns. Examples of this can be found in the LMS collection held by the School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London, England.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: As with orthodoxy checks, visiting missionaries would sometimes observe or take part in services. Letters to the directors of the LMS in England would note anything which they considered questionable. There were several incidences of this occurring in Demerara. Examples of this can be found in the LMS collection held by the School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London, England.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although it is common in a number of Protestant Christian groups to refer to other members as "brother" or "sister," this has not been documented for this group. However, it is possible the members used this terminology among themselves, but lack of written sources from the mostly enslaved participants makes this unknown.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Enslaved workers, mostly plantation.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The group's adherents were primarily enslaved workers. Some food was provided by slaveowners, but was often lacking in quantity and quality.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Most of the group were enslaved workers.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Most of the group were enslaved workers. Very few reached old age and those who became infirm received very little care, often dying. While many plantations had a building which they termed a "sick house" which was under plantation management, little care was actually given. See incidents in the Journal of John Smith, cited above in Sources.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Groups in England protested the plight of the mostly enslaved group, but there was no relief available. Many plantations had what was termed a "sick house," little care was actually given.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: One of the purposes of the missionaries was to teach participants to read the Bible. This was particularly contentious with slaveowners who believed literacy among the enslaved to be dangerous and likely to lead to rebellion. See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith and the Life and Labors of John Wray, cited above in Sources.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Missionaries and literate parishioners taught members, but this was often hampered by slaveowners opposed to educating bondspeople.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: The missionary's wife would often teach both males and females literacy, and additionally some skills such as sewing for females.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: Although missionaries acted as teachers, in some cases, such as in Berbice, they did this for bondspeople employed at the garrison at the request of officials.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The missionary had several deacons who would report to him.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: LMS missionaries were required to receive approval from the governor of the colony for various endeavours such as building usage, time and place of meetings, following advice at times of epidemic disease, etc. See various incidents in the Journal of John Smith, cited in Sources.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: The mostly enslaved members produced crops for plantation owners to sell.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: This answer is qualified in that the members were primarily enslaved labourers on plantations. An important aspect of their labour was clearing canals and other waterways which were numerous in the colony, and working with drainage and irrigation for crops. Most of this was to keep individual plantations profitable, but there were bondspeople owned by the government who would work on public waterways. See Higman, B. W. "Slave Populations of the British Caribbean: 1807-1834," (Barbados: University of the West Indies Press, 1995): 164.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management was the job of any enslaved labourers assigned to it, whether or not they belonged to this group. They were under orders from either plantation managers or government officials. See Thompson, Alvin O. "Unprofitable Servants: Crown Slaves in Berbice, Guyana 1803-1831" (Barbados: University of West Indies Press, 2002): 14.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: As with water management, enslaved workers who were members of this group or not and were assigned to the job worked on transportation infrastructure insofar as piloting boats, poling or rowing.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other

than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As with water management, any enslaved labourer assigned to work in transportation would do so, whether part of the religious group or not. This would include piloting boats, poling or rowing.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Although donations were appreciated, there were no tithes as most of the group were enslaved people who lived in extreme poverty.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The only qualification to this would be for the few free persons attached to the group.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Missionaries and freemen could be called for militia duty in certain situations, and they were subject to policing by militia and regular military.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: All members of the colony, free and enslaved, were subject to the laws of the British government and that of its representative, the governor.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: The only penalties for infractions within the group were being denied membership.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Execution was fairly common, especially for bondpeople.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Occasionally enslaved people would be exiled from the colony. This would sever them from all family and friends and could result in a more onerous situation than previously.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Whipping and other punishments were extremely common among the enslaved for infractions of the law.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There does not seem to be any documented evidence of ostracism serving as an institutionalized punishment.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: As far as members of the religious group go, because most were enslaved, and others such as the missionary would have little property to speak of, this was not applicable. However, during the 1823 rebellion in Demerara, missionary John Smith was arrested and money and personal papers seized. Much of this, including the money, was not returned to his widow, although the legality of this was questionable. For further information, see London Missionary Society, Report of the Proceedings Against the Late Rev. J. Smith of Demerara, Minister of the Gospel, Who Was Tried Under Martial Law, and Condemned to Death, in a Charge of Aiding and Assisting in a Rebellion of the Negro Slaves; From a Full and Correct Copy, Transmitted to England by Mr. Smith's Counsel, and Including the Documentary Evidence Omitted in the Parliamentary Copy; With an Appendix; Containing the Letters and Statements of Mr. and Mrs. Smith, Mrs. Elliot, Mr. Arrindell, &c.; and, also, the Society's Petition to the House of Commons. London: F. Westley, 1824. <https://www.loc.gov/item/03000059/>

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The only code, per se, was implied by Christian precepts, but these were not a legal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The laws of England and its representative in the colony (governor).

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The missionary and any freemen belonging to the group could be required to participate in the colony's militia.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They were subject to the British regular military and the colony's militia. Theoretically, they were probably protected by them, but the situation did not arise and were, in fact, used against them during the 1823 rebellion.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: They used English.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They used English. Many of the group's adherents were illiterate, but a number were taught literacy by the missionary, his wife, and other group members. The purpose of teaching the group literacy was to enable them to read the Bible, but naturally this ability was used for any written material available.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They used English. While many of the group's adherents were illiterate, a number were taught by the missionary, his wife, and other group members. The specified purpose was to learn to read the Bible, but naturally was used for any written material available.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The group used the same calendar based on the Julian calendar as other Western Christian groups.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same Julian-based calendar was used throughout the Western Christian world.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: See answers below.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The majority of the group were enslaved in an agricultural society. While food was grown, most crops were sold as commodities by the plantation owners. Some of the enslaved were given small plots of land on which to grow food, but in practice, their time was often so taken up with work for the slaveowner that they did not have time to tend to raising their own food. Waterways ran throughout the colony and fish were likely abundant, but as with crops, fishing for food would depend on time and energy available. Food was supplied to some extent by owners, but usually not enough and not of sufficient quality. Markets were very important to the enslaved population for trading any surplus items and providing some variety of foodstuffs. See daCosta, "Crowns of Glory" cited in Sources: 39-86.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See answer below.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Slaveowners supplied the enslaved members with some food, but it was often not enough and lacking in variety. Some of this was grown locally, which would require slave labour to produce, and some was purchased from shipments brought in from across the British Atlantic, such as dried fish from what is now the Canadian Maritime provinces.